

- **Infrastructure** - This node represents the risk with the project's infrastructure - the network, environment, application servers, and storage database.
- **Environment** - This node represents the risk with the project's development environment.
- **Server** - This node represents the risk with the project's application server.
- **Data** - This node represents the risk with the project's database.
- **Integration** - This node represents the risk of integrating the system with the legacy and third parties.
- **Third-party** - This node represents the risk of integrating the system with third parties.
- **Legacy** - This node represents the risk of integrating the system with the legacy.
- **Service** - This node represents the risk of using services (APIs, Frameworks) from external platforms.
- **Support** - This node represents the risk of the technical community's lack of support with third-party technologies.
- **Application** - This node represents the risk with the application.
- **Method** - This node represents the risk with the proposed solution method for application development.
- **Technique** - This node represents the risk with the technique (Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Blockchain) to be implemented in the application.
- **Validation** - This node represents the risk with the validation (need for specific environment or data) of the application's method.
- **Architecture** - This node represents the architectural risk for the development of the system.
- **Security** - This node represents the security risk (cryptography, digital certificate, tokens) for system development.
- **Efficiency** - This node represents the risk of application efficiency.
- **Size** - This node represents the risk of space required for application about the size of tables and cache that the system will need.
- **Performance** - This node represents the necessary performance risk for the application for the number of users that will access the system.